

TORSIONAL FATIGUE BEHAVIOR
OF GRAPHITE-EPOXY CYLINDERS

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The effects of fiber orientation on torsional fatigue life were studied for graphite-epoxy cylinders. The fiber orientations used were parallel to the longitudinal cylindrical axis and at angles of ± 45 degrees to the axis. Torsional stress for the ± 45 degree tubes at equivalent numbers of failure cycles were almost 4 times as high as those for longitudinal tubes.

For both orientations, the slopes of the S-N curves were very steep and close to parallel to each other. However, a plot of shear strain vs. fatigue cycles indicated that shear strain is a more sensitive parameter to describe fatigue life than torsional stress in cylinders. Also, shear strain of cylinders at any given time during fatigue indicates the remaining life of the component independent of the fiber orientation.

Residual torsional strength tests subsequent to fatigue failure show that longitudinal specimens retain a much greater amount of strength and stiffness than basket-weave specimens because of the "broomstick effect", which causes a more restrictive mode of failure in the longitudinal specimens.

Introduction

Small variations in stress levels make prediction of fatigue cycles to failure difficult because of the high degree of sensitivity in number of cycles to magnitude of stress. This is indicated by a very flat slope, dS/dN , on the S-N curve (1). Also, variations in construction of cross-ply or bias-orientated laminates necessitate the generation of different S-N curves for fatigue design purposes, because the difference in effect of fiber orientation causes different stress endurance levels at equivalent numbers of fatigue cycles (2).

The object of this paper is to examine another parameter to describe fatigue life in order to reduce the high cyclic sensitivity and to find out if orientation effects can be normalized by observing a parameter other than stress. The parameter chosen is shear strain, which is obtained by measuring the angle of twist of the thin-walled cylindrical specimens over a known length.

Fiber orientation in composites plays an important role in retention of residual strength after fatigue failure. An examination of the differences in the modes of fatigue failure explains why longitudinally reinforced cylinders retain a great deal more residual strength than basket-weave reinforced cylinders even though the latter are much stronger in torsional fatigue.

Material Fabrication

The specimens used in these experiments were fabricated in the form of hollow cylinders. All tubes were manufactured by using Modulite 5206 (3), a 350-degree F curing, temperature-resistant, modified epoxy system coated on "Modmor" Type II high-strength carbon fibers.

The longitudinal tubes are described by orientation of the fibers at zero degrees to the longitudinal axis of the cylinder. These specimens were fabricated using the vacuum-bag autoclave process (4, 5). Four plies were wrapped around a mandrel and placed inside an autoclave system, cured for two hours at 350 degrees F and 100 psi pressure and post-cured for two hours at 400 degrees F under restraint.

The basket-weave tube fibers were orientated at ± 45 degrees to the cylindrical axis. These tubes were fabricated using a filament winding technique (4, 6, 7). The pre-impregnated tape was wound around a mandrel in a ± 45 degree pattern until four plies were reached. Since no autoclave is used in filamentary winding, the cylinders were wrapped with one-inch wide mylar tape (12% shrink on heating) and left on the winder for 15 minutes under four infrared lamps, in order to exert some pressure on the cylinders during the cure. The specimens in this condition were cured for two hours under the tape pressure and cooled in the oven to room temperature overnight.

Test Procedures

Both types of specimens were four plies thick. Each specimen used was trimmed to an 8-inch (200mm) length, chosen by optimizing a finite length with regard to end effects. The specimens were mounted on a plug and clamp system designed for proper adhesion to the specimens.

The adhesive coating between plugs and specimen was a resin system composed of Shell Epon 828 resin with General Mills Versamid 140 polyamide hardener mixed in equal parts. The adhesive joints were cured at room temperature for 48 hours before specimens were tested.

In earlier trials testing the bond strength of the resin adhesive, it was found that hose clamps attached to the outer surfaces at the plug ends helped minimize premature bond failure of the joints during fatigue testing, so this procedure was continued.

In considering the effects of the hose clamps on the end attachments of the cylinders, a shell analysis by Whitney, Grimes and Francis (8) indicated that end clamping had little effect on torsional loading and that shear strengths obtained under clamp restraints were compatible with values obtained by other methods.

The effects of length on laminated thin-walled cylinders were investigated by Vicario and Rizzo (9). Their results indicated that for thin-walled tubes under combined loading the effects of end restraints are confined to only small regions near the ends. Finite tubes were comparable to infinitely

long tubes when the ratio of thickness to inside diameter, t/D_i , was less than 0.05 and length to inside diameter, L/D_i , was greater than 3. For this reason, the arbitrary length of 8 inches (200mm) was considered acceptable, giving a value of $L/D_i = 4$. The maximum value of t/D_i was 0.035, so both ratios were adequate for testing purposes.

Mechanical Testing

Static torsion tests were performed on a Tinius-Olsen Torsion Test Machine at a constant revolution speed of 5 degrees per minute. The test setup is pictured in Figure 1. During Testing, a record of torque in inch-pounds vs. twist angle in degrees was made for each specimen.

Fig. 1 - Tinius Olsen Static Torsion Test Machine

Fatigue tests were performed on a Sonntag SF-1U Fatigue Testing Machine using the torsion fixture with a lever arm 6-1/4 inches (160mm) long. The test setup, shown in Figure 2, displays a filament-wound tubular graphite-epoxy specimen and the clamp arrangement used to help prevent premature failures between the specimens and the plug fixtures. During fatigue testing a record of applied cyclic load in pounds and amplitude of lever arm movement in inches were kept.

The criterion for fatigue failure was a limiting amplitude of the lever

Fig. 2 - Sonntag SF-1U Fatigue Testing Machine

arm. Once the specimens lost enough rigidity during the fatigue tests to allow a deflection of 1/2 inch (13mm) or a twist angle of 4-1/2 degrees corresponding to a shear strain of 0.01, the specimens were considered failed in fatigue.

After the specimens were failed in fatigue, static torsion tests were performed on the Tinius-Olson Machine to determine the residual torsional strength. Again, a record of torque vs. twist angle was made for each specimen.

Table I. Static Torsion Data

Tube Type	No.	Maximum Torque, In.-Lb.	Maximum Stress, psi	Maximum Twist Angle, Degrees	Maximum Shear Strain
Longitudinal	GL-11	2143	7,950	7.2	0.1257
	GS-12	2380	8,420	9.6	0.1676
Basket-Weave	G2-A	7020	27,400	11.6	0.2025
	G2-A	6650	27,300	10.4	0.1815

Results and Discussion

Mechanical Properties

The results of static torsion testing for both types of specimens appear in Table I. For four-ply longitudinal graphite-epoxy tubes, Grimes et al (10) reported static ultimate shear stresses between 7.57 and 10.5 ksi. Our results are 7.95 and 8.42 ksi. For static \pm 45 degree graphite torsion tubes, Pinckney and Freeman (11) reported an average of 25.7 ksi, compared to our results of 27.3 and 27.4 ksi.

Fatigue values for the longitudinal specimens appear in Table II, and those for the basket-weave specimens in Table III. The data for stress and fatigue cycles for each specimen orientation were analyzed separately in a log-log linear least-squares analysis. The data points and the least-squares approximation are shown in Figure 3. The slope, dN/dS , is -12.5 for the longitudinal specimens and -11.4 for the basket-weave specimens. Both values of dN/dS clearly indicate the narrow band of stress levels over many orders of magnitude for cyclic fatigue life. Also, because of fiber orientation, the stress levels of the basket-weave specimens are approximately four times as high as the longitudinal specimens at equivalent cycles.

Table II. Longitudinal Fatigue Data

Tube No.	Stress, psi	Fatigue Cycles	Shear Strain
3	2,320	362,000 (stopped)	2.918×10^{-3}
	3,480	4,000	4,481 "
GL- 3	4,635	1,500	7.502 "
GL- 4	2,263	20,460,000 (runout)	3.025 "
	3,394	22,000	5.528 "
GL- 5	3,477	30,000	4.56 "
GL- 6	3,090	16,000	4.37 "
GL- 7	3,315	21,000	5.43 "
GL- 8	2,716	20,842,000 (runout)	3.546 "
	3,168	139,000	5.48 "
GL- 9	3,094	16,000,000 (runout)	4.594 "
	3,978	6,500	7.726 "
GL-10	3,757	5,000	5.429 "

Table III. Basket-Weave Fatigue Data

Tube No.	Stress, psi	Fatigue Cycles	Shear Strain
G4-A	3,425	37,417,000 (runout)	1.391×10^{-3}
	5,480	5,327,000	2.247 "
G4-B	7,060	16,861,000	2.777 "
G5-A	12,780	122,000	3.791 "
G5-B	14,600	19,000	4.633 "
G5-C	13,700	16,000	4.423 "
G6-A	12,540	8,000	4.005 "

Fig. 3 - Torsional S-N curve of graphite-epoxy specimens

The results of residual static torsion testing for the longitudinal and basket-weave specimens may be found in Table IV. Although the basket-weave specimens exhibited almost four times as much torsional fatigue shear strength as the longitudinal specimens, the former had lost a great deal of stiffness from delamination and fiber fracture in the ± 45 degree directions. Therefore, the residual strength values of the basket-weave cylinders have dropped to 3 - 5% of the virgin static ultimate shear strength, an almost complete loss of strength. However, the longitudinal specimens indicate a 50 - 80% retention of virgin strength. Because of the longitudinal fiber orientation, fatigue failure is restricted to one major crack lengthwise along the cylindrical axis and several minor cracks parallel to the major one. Therefore, the residual strength values for longitudinal specimens are high in comparison to the virgin strength.

Not only did the longitudinal specimens retain a greater percentage of their initial strength, but also the absolute values of their residual strength after fatigue were much higher than those for the basket-weave specimens. In simple terms, the longitudinal specimens can be compared to a broomstick, and the basket-weave specimens to a "Chinese Finger Trap", the device which is woven in a basket-weave pattern and expands on compression and contracts on tension, because of the shear action on the fibers. In torsion of a broomstick, strength and stiffness are maintained until many

Table IV. Residual Strength Data

Tube Type	No.	Test Stress, psi	Fatigue Cycles	Residual Strength, psi	
Longitudinal	GL-3	4,635	1,500	6,300	
	GL-4	3,394	22,000	4,320	
	GL-5	3,477	30,000	5,040	
	GL-6	3,090	16,000	4,300	
	GL-7	3,315	21,000	4,630	
	GL-8	3,168	139,000	4,638	
	GL-9	3,978	6,500	4,089	
	GL-10	3,757	5,000	5,746	
	Basket-Weave	G4-B	7,060	16,861,000	797
		G5-B	14,600	19,000	771
G5-C		13,700	16,000	573	
G6-A		12,540	8,000	1,012	

fibers delaminate. Once this is accomplished, the specimen fails. Since the longitudinal specimen had retained a great deal of its stiffness, strength and fibrous integrity subsequent to the restrictive fatigue failure, the residual strength was high. In the basket-weave specimens, however, the delamination process and fiber fracture caused a great loss of stiffness and strength after fatigue failure. Thus, the "broomstick effect" on the longitudinal specimens retained a much greater amount of strength and stiffness than the "Chinese Finger Trap Effect" on the basket-weave specimens.

Failure Mode

Figure 4 shows a longitudinal specimen in two stages of a static torsion test. Figure 4(a) indicates cracking and delamination along the longitudinal axis in several locations at maximum torque during the static torsion test. Figure 4(b) shows buckling after instability. All longitudinal specimens failed in a similar manner with several cracks propagating parallel to the cylindrical axis.

Fig. 4 - Longitudinal specimen during static torsion test:
 (a) At maximum torque. (b) Beyond instability.

The delamination and fiber fracture can be seen readily in the typical failures of basket-weave cylinders shown in Figure 5.

(b)
Fig. 5 - Basket-weave specimens failed in static torsion

The fatigue failures of longitudinal specimens shown in Figure 6 indicate signs of crazing of the matrix as evidenced by the powdery trail along the longitudinal cracks. The crazing progressed continuously as the cracks propagated through the specimens longitudinally.

(a)
Fig. 6 - Longitudinal Specimen fatigue failures

(b)

Fig. 6 - cont'd

The basket-weave specimens displayed in Figure 7 show failure by delamination and cracking along the ± 45 degree lines. The delamination process progressively deteriorated the specimen integrity during the fatigue test.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7 - Basket-weave specimen fatigue failures

Figure 8 shows longitudinal specimens after residual strength tests. The failure mode was similar to that of the virgin static specimens with the exception that the specimen was already damaged by previous fatigue failure. The specimens exhibit several cracks which have propagated parallel to the cylindrical axis.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 - Longitudinal specimens after residual strength tests

(a)

(b)

Fig. 9 - Basket-weave specimens after residual strength tests

Figure 9 indicates basket-weave specimens after residual strength tests. Since the fatigue tests had caused so much progressive delamination and fiber fracture, the complete residual test failures occurred at very low shear stresses.

Shear Strain Analysis

The shear strains were monitored at the beginning of cycling and periodically during the fatigue tests. The values of the initial strains, γ_i , appear in Tables II and III. Initial shear strain vs. cycles to failure for both types of specimens are shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10 - $\gamma_i - N_f$ curve for graphite-epoxy specimens

The slope in Figure 10, $dN_f/d\gamma_i$, has a value of -6.4, meaning that there is not as large a variation in fatigue life as a function of initial strain as compared to shear stress. Also, a specimen with longitudinal fiber orientation, although failing at a lower torsional stress, displays approximately the same shear strain as a basket-weave specimen at an equivalent number of fatigue cycles to failure. Thus, differences in strength caused by different fiber orientation can be normalized by the shear strain behavior of the material.

During the fatigue tests, changes in strain were recorded as a function of remaining fatigue life. The results appear in Table V. The plot for instantaneous shear strain, γ , vs. remaining life, $(N_f - N)$, is shown in Figure 11. The slope, $d(N_f - N)/d\gamma$, has the same value, -6.4, as that for $dN_f/d\gamma_i$ from Figure 10. The instantaneous shear strain, γ , increases as the test proceeds, and the decrease in remaining life may be read from the graph. This signifies that remaining fatigue life of cylinders may be predicted by monitoring the shear strain at any time during the life of the specimens.

Since the shear strains change during the deterioration of the specimens in fatigue while the torsional stresses remain constant, the shear modulus must vary. Since initial shear strains describe the fatigue life in the same manner as the instantaneous shear strains in describing remaining life, the deterioration process must initiate early during fatigue and progress continuously until ultimate fatigue failure.

Table V. Torsional Shear Strain and Remaining Life Data

Tube Type	No.	Stress, psi	Fatigue Cycles	Remaining Life Cycles	Shear Strain
Longitudinal	3	3,480	0	4,000	4.481×10^{-3}
		"	4,000	0	Failure
GL-2	8,840	8,840	0	500	8.352×10^{-3}
		"	500	0	Failure
GL-3	4,635	4,635	0	1,500	7.502×10^{-3}
		"	1,000	500	8.336 "
		"	1,500	0	Failure
GL-4	3,395	3,395	0	22,000	5.528×10^{-3}
		"	16,000	6,000	5.841 "
		"	20,000	2,000	6.258 "
		"	21,000	1,000	7.927 "
		"	22,000	0	Failure
GL-5	3,477	3,477	0	30,000	4.560×10^{-3}
		"	800	29,200	5.002 "
		"	11,000	19,000	5.418 "
		"	30,000	0	Failure
GL-6	3,090	3,090	0	16,000	4.372×10^{-3}
		"	3,000	13,000	5.205 "
		"	5,000	11,000	5.413 "
		"	7,000	9,000	5.830 "
		"	8,000	8,000	6.662 "
		"	13,000	3,000	7.079 "
		"	14,000	2,000	7.912 "
		"	14,800	1,200	8.744 "
		"	15,000	1,000	9.577 "
		"	16,000	0	Failure
		GL-7	3,315	3,315	0
"	9,000			12,000	5.638 "
"	10,000			11,000	5.846 "
"	16,000			5,000	6.055 "
"	19,000			2,000	6.264 "
"	20,000			1,000	6.682 "
"	20,200			800	7.517 "
"	20,800			200	10.440 "
"	21,000			0	Failure
GL-8	3,168	3,168	0	139,000	5.841×10^{-3}
		"	64,000	75,000	6.049 "
		"	119,000	20,000	6.258 "
		"	137,000	2,000	10.430 "
		"	139,000	0	Failure
GL-9	3,978	3,978	0	6,500	7.726×10^{-3}
		"	2,000	4,500	7.934 "
		"	3,000	3,500	8.143 "
		"	4,000	2,500	8.352 "
		"	5,000	1,500	8.770 "
		"	6,000	500	9.396 "
		"	6,100	400	10.440 "
		"	6,500	0	Failure

Table V. (Continued)

Tube Type	No.	Stress, psi	Fatigue Cycles	Remaining Life, Cycles	Shear Strain
Longitudinal	GL-10	3,757	0	5,000	5.429×10^{-3}
			300	4,700	6.055 "
			1,000	4,000	6.264 "
			2,000	3,000	6.473 "
			3,000	2,000	6.682 "
			4,000	1,000	7.099 "
			4,800	200	8.352 "
		5,000	0	Failure	
Basket-Weave	G4-A	5,480	0	5,327,000	2.247×10^{-3}
			5,327,000	0	Failure
	G4-B	7,060	0	16,861,000	2.777×10^{-3}
			8,000,000	8,861,000	2.990 "
			10,566,000	6,295,000	2.990 "
			16,861,000	0	Failure
	G5-A	12,780	0	122,000	3.791×10^{-3}
			35,000	87,000	4.001 "
			43,000	79,000	4.212 "
			122,000	0	Failure
	G5-B	14,600	0	19,000	4.633×10^{-3}
			19,000	0	Failure
	G5-C	13,700	0	16,000	4.423×10^{-3}
			16,000	0	Failure
G6-A	12,540	0	8,000	4.005×10^{-3}	
		8,000	0	Failure	

Fig. 11 - $\gamma - (N_f - N)$ curve for graphite-epoxy specimens

Conclusions

Based on the experimental data obtained herein, the following conclusions can be made:

1. Fatigue failure of graphite-epoxy composite cylinders in torsion indicates an extremely flat slope, dS/dN , on the S-N curves. Failure involves a continuous deterioration process of delamination between the epoxy and the graphite fibers and also between layers of ply.

2. Monitoring shear strain instead of shear stress and plotting the results on a γ -N curve instead of an S-N curve gives a more sensitive measurement in control of fatigue life.

3. Although fatigue life as a function of torsional stress is highly dependent on fiber orientation in cylinders, shear strains describe fatigue life independent of fiber orientation.

4. The cumulative effects of shear strain on the remaining life describe the fatigue life of cylinders the same as the initial shear strains, so strain readings taken at any time can indicate the remaining fatigue life of the cylinders.

5. Although longitudinal specimens exhibit much lower strength in torsional fatigue than basket-weave specimens, the former retain a greater percentage of their original strength and stiffness subsequent to fatigue failure because of the more restrictive mode of failure in the longitudinal direction.

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